

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: S12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country

Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia

(engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au)

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Keynote

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking to local government and/or relevant authorities of Bangladesh to monitor to assess the administrative functions and official misconducts of government employees. A few reports by Professor Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain in practical life journey is being coalesced and reported to eliminate official crimes in the local government offices of Bangladesh. By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death people in a country. This report demonstrates the functions, contributions and limitations of the local government for the right goal of the government service. Every person believes government officer. So, every government officer should be ethical and ethical. Under the democratic theory of a country, citizens or publics take the living and food responsibilities of the government officers. Therefore, every ethical person or political leader or government officer should continue the right way of the leading power on behalf of a government on behalf of the public. Every office of a government officer is the personal executive office of every citizen. Every chair of a government officer is the personal executive chair of every public. But the government officer is holding an ethical responsibility under the acknowledgment of his/her personal excellency and ethical beauty. It should be proved that a government officer is more ethical than a general citizen or public of any country all over the world without which the excellency of a democratic government may be seriously hampered and misguided, the excellency of a

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

government officer may be hindered and interrupted. In general, every government officer should be individually responsible for proving the personal excellency and ethical beauty as a unit of a democratic government. Customer service or public service is the key requirement of a government officer, political leaders, and public administration. Therefore, this report on the occurrence in Bangladesh is being supported by Australian federal register of legislation, Australian public service (APS) act 1999, section 15, breaches of the code of conduct and Bangladeshi penal code of Bangladesh public service (BPS), 1860 (act no. IX of 1860, 161; act no. XLV of 1860, 120B, 415). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to approach to the Bangladesh government to improve research and development of the public service. Every public is also the legal part of every public administration of a democratic government. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was trying to sell his local land property to manage his PhD research costs in Australia and, accordingly, he was dealing with Bangladeshi land officers for the purpose of document preparation. In general principle of democracy; every front desk of a public service is the office of a prime minister, every front desk of a public service is the office of a president, every front desk of a public service is the office of a public or citizen, every front desk of a public service is the office of a public service commission. A president is a single person (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k), a prime minister is a single person, a minister is a single person who can not visit the whole front desk of their public service departments. Public service administration of Bangladesh may invest in research and development of quality enhancement of public service. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is proposed a penalty/compensation award of 55,000USD (in words: fifty-five thousand USD) or an approved percentage of the total penalty to the public administration of local government in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also proposing his theory of economy to minimize currency inflation in Bangladesh.

Proposal of legal act and/or outcomes of the crime analysis

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is proposing a victim-friendly penalty act of every government.

1. Every public or victim will get 80% of the total approved penalty unit for the time investment, crime reporting, crime analysis support, and compensation.
2. Every legal practitioner will get 10% of the total approved penalty unit for the time investment, reporting, and crime analysis.
3. Every government will get 10% of the total approved penalty unit for the administrative charge and magistracy cost.
4. Every crime offender will be liable to pay 100% of the total approved penalty unit for the support of crime analysis.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCCM College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

5. Every government officer/public service officer should have lifetime imprisonment for their intentional crime in government office and public care/nursing centre.
6. Every public/citizen should get a compensation award or a percentage of the penalty unit or a percentage of the penalty income of the government for the service of crime investigation at government office if the public/citizen is not a relevant administrative employee if the public/citizen is not a paid employee.

Keywords

Public administration, public service, penalty, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Letter of proceeding to the local government of Bangladesh to the public administration of Bangladesh to the political leaders of Bangladesh from the office of Nobel Nominee Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Date 7 July 2025

To
Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Iunus, Economist
Chief Advisor
Office of Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Iunus
The People's Republic of Bangladesh
yunus@yunuscentre.org
psecy@cao.gov.bd
majumderali1950@gmail.com
musfiquldu33@gmail.com
psecy@cao.gov.bd
secretary@cao.gov.bd
seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd
lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd

Mr. Asif Mahmud Shojib Bhuiyan

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Advisor

Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Co-operatives

The People's Republic of Bangladesh

adviser.lgrdc@lgd.gov.bd

ps.adviser.lgrdc@lgd.gov.bd

moajjam97531@gmail.com

pro.lgrdc@lgd.gov.bd

Page | 4

Dr. Muhammad Mukhlesur Rahman

Senior Secretary

Ministry of Public Administration

The People's Republic of Bangladesh

secretary@mopa.gov.bd

info@lgd.gov.bd

addlwing@mopa.gov.bd

Professor Dr. Mobasser Monem

Chairman, Bangladesh Public Service Commission

The People's Republic of Bangladesh

ps_chairman@bpsc.gov.bd

potochairmanbpsc@gmail.com

mobassermonem@du.ac.bd

pubad@du.ac.bd

Dr. Mohammad Abdul Momen

Chairman, Anti-Corruption Commission

The People's Republic of Bangladesh

chairman@acc.org.bd

commissioner.inv@acc.org.bd

commissioner.inq@acc.org.bd

secretary@acc.org.bd

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Dr. Salehuddin Ahmed, Economist
Advisor
Ministry of finance, The People's Republic of Bangladesh
adviser@finance.gov.bd
mofizuli1@finance.gov.bd
mkrahman79@finance.gov.bd
secretary@finance.gov.bd

ASM Saleh Ahmed (translated from Bengali)
Senior Secretary, Ministry of Land, The People's Republic of Bangladesh
secretary@minland.gov.bd
aharish2169@gmail.com

Dear central administrative concern of Bangladesh government,
Your honour for your public service to Bangladesh government.
Your honour for your quality service to Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh.

1 Introduction

The wealth is accumulating and accumulating so much due to human force, human violence, political violence, and human trapping. Some people want to get the wealth of the whole world, but they can not enjoy the whole wealth, but they die and die. So, everyone is not getting job support, food support, marriage/sex support, and living cost support of a government. Actually, the wealth has no limitations, we have enough wealth, the whole people are facing the limitations of proper management and human beauty. People are bombing and bombing in the planet, but the whole people are not getting the quality support of governments. So, we are self-challenging our self-surviving against the peace of mankind. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is afraid and afraid about what is happening.

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. Every citizen pays to the government through tax, inflation, heritage/successor, and multidimensional ways of daily service. By nature, nobody can carry or enjoy his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature, somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death people in terms

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

of government and/or family. Somehow, every government is serving for the right distribution of the wealth to the public. Practically and naturally, everybody wants more wealth, controlling financial desire is also so tough. Sometimes, desire turns to the limitless and crimes. Therefore, people try to accumulate more money in their self-pocket. Sometimes, power versus financial achievement climbs parallelly, rapidly, and proportionally. People tend to the practice crime or accumulate money against the peace of human beings. Later, people die and die to satisfy the order of nature, the unseen government, and/or creator of the religious people. Unfortunately, and naturally, people can not keep money with them after death. Automatically, wealth turns to the inheritance of the government wealth and/or family members and/or other people. This is the strange philosophy of human beings. Nobody can disrespect or restrict or deny the philosophy of the death and the natural loss of wealth. Therefore, if government keeps the whole inheritance of the death people of the country to distribute the living and food support or income support to the community people, there is also limitation in terms of ethics of top management, there is also scope to continue research and development in Bangladesh or democratic countries. We have enough wealth. But we can not distribute wealth properly due to the practical attitude of human beings due to a lack of the national and international policy.

Page | 6

1.1 Union council, city council, and land office of Bangladesh government

The city council or union council is the heart of a local government. A city council or union council has a value for the peace of people. Therefore, every chairman and member of city council or union council should have official education or a bachelor degree or an ethical grade point of local service. Therefore, the service of the city council or union council may be extended for a transparent support to the local people. Land is the major tax and revenue-earning platform of the Bangladesh government. The earnings of a government and the expenditure of a specific ministry should have transparent follow-up to minimize the currency inflation of a country.

1.2 Every public or citizen should be an active unit of public administration of a democratic country

Public service officers are the permanent category. Political leaders serve and control the government officers for a specific duration of time. The key responsibility of a political government is to foster the ethical standard for public care and public service through permanent category government officers of a country. So, the ethical practices in public administration are more beneficial to ensure quality public service of a country. Every government officer is a unit of a public administration. Similarly, every public or citizen is also a unit of public administration. Accordingly, this research is being focused on and forwarded to satisfy the principle of a democratic government. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) would like to assess, notify and dedicate a few moments and a few comments in the local government offices of Bangladesh if the government can try to eliminate

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh: ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

further crime under the ethical support of the Bangladesh government through the interim government and/or political government.

1.3 Limitation in democracy and Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain proposed the modification in democratic election and selection process of a government

Democracy of illiterate people mainly lead by discussion media/hearing/speaker support. So, more people know the political leaders rather than the top administrative people of a government. So, there is a limitation to the democratic principle for the right implementation of a government. The present practice of democratic principle is termed as one public = one vote = one government = one president. The discussion and understanding of the quality of a person may hinder or decline to judge the quality of a political leader. These are also permanent limitations of democracy. Bangladesh government and the democratic government may implement the Dr. Anowar's theory of democracy (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024w).

2 Methodology

The public administration, local government, land office, passport and immigration office, hospital, bank, union council, road construction, currency inflation, government officers, political leaders, office of president (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k), office of chief advisor (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k), office of university grant commission (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025b), and administrative crimes in public service and public nursing centre have been accumulated and remarked for the right management, public service commission, criminal/crime-free administration, and development theory of Bangladesh (2014-2025). The information was collected and remarked by Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain during his practical life journey in Bangladesh.

3 Results and discussions

Table 1. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is proposing penalty of 55,000USD (in words: fifty five thousand USD) to the public service offices of Bangladesh government (M. A. Hossain, 2023c).

Name of posts and offices	Crime types	Recommendation	Proposed penalty	Year
Administrative officer, office of Mirzapur	➤ Additional earnings of money if he is a paid employee of	✓ Investigation and counselling or	5000 USD	2024

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

<p>Union Parishad, Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh</p>	<p>Bangladesh government.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ He was taking an official money without providing official invoice or money receipt or revenue evidence from the Bangladesh government. ➤ Let's excuse him if he is a non-paid employee of Bangladesh government. 	<p>training of public administration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Administrative follow up of the top management 		
<p>Administrative officer, office of Mirzapur Union Parishad, Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Additional earnings of money if he is a paid employee of Bangladesh government. ➤ Possibly, he was making a fake document to receive a duplicate bill or duplicate invoice from the Bangladesh government. Possibly, it was an amount of five digits. ➤ Possibly, he was making a fake document in his office at the front desk of a public service centre. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration. ✓ Administrative follow up of the top management. 	<p>5000USD and termination of the job</p>	<p>2024</p>

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Possibly, he was making a fake document in front of a local client or public in a public care centre. It seems that he is habituated to doing illegal and official responsibilities. These are the symptoms of high-risk misconduct against the morality of public service and against the morality of a democratic government. 			
<p>Sub-assistant land officer, Mohonpur land office, Mirzapur Union Parishad, office of assistant commissioner (land), Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Additional earnings of money if he is a paid employee of Bangladesh government. ➤ He was taking official money or additional money without providing an official invoice or money receipt or revenue evidence of Bangladesh government. ➤ One day, the office was closed at 10:00-10:30 am. There was service interruption without notice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration. ✓ Administrative follow up of the top management 	<p>5000USD</p>	<p>2024</p>

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Let's excuse him if he is a non-paid employee of Bangladesh government. 			
Registrar, office of sub-registrar, Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Additional earnings of money if he is a paid employee of Bangladesh government. ➤ He was taking official money without providing an official invoice or money receipt or revenue evidence of Bangladesh government. ➤ Late attendance and/or service interruption without notice on 10 February 2025 ➤ Let's excuse him if he is a non-paid employee of Bangladesh government. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration ✓ Administrative follow up of the top management 	5000 USD	2023-2024
Assistant officer or office assistant, sub-registrar office, Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Additional earnings of money if he is a paid employee of Bangladesh government for documents or registrar searching in the sub-registrar office. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration ✓ Administrative follow up of 	5000 USD	2023-2024

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Lecturer & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ He was taking official money without providing an official invoice or money receipt or revenue evidence of Bangladesh government. ➤ Let's excuse him if he is a non-paid employee of Bangladesh government. 	the top management		
Assistant commissioner (land), Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Late attendance and/or service interruption in office without notice on 10 February 2025. ➤ Lack of controlling the whole office on 10 February 2025. ➤ Lack of controlling sub-registrar office and sub-assistant land office who are taking money without the evidence of revenue or money receipt of government 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration ✓ Administrative follow up of the top management 	5000USD	2025
First Security Islami Bank (FSIB), Rangs RD center, block: SE (F), plot:03, Gulshan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Created service interruption to issue money to the public/citizens/Profess or Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without notice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration 	5000 USD	2024

Avenue, Dhaka-1212.		➤ Administrative follow up of the top management		
Office of university grant commission (UGC); Plot#E-18/A, Agargaon Administrative Area, Sher-e-Bangla Nagar, Dhaka-1207 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025b).	➤ Created service interruption of e-mail receiving from public/citizen/Professor or Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without notice.	➤ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration ➤ Administrative follow up of the top management	5000 USD	2025
Office of president, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh; Bangabhaban, Dhaka (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k).	➤ Created service interruption of e-mail receiving from public/citizen/Professor or Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without notice.	➤ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration ➤ Administrative follow up of the top management	5000 USD	2025
Office of chief advisor, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh; governance innovation unit, office of prime minister, Tejgaon,	➤ Created service interruption of e-mail receiving from public/citizen/Professor or Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without notice.	➤ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration ➤ Administrative follow up of	5000 USD	2025

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: S12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Dhaka-1215 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k).		the top management		
Office of national human rights commission, 9 th floor, BTMC Bhaban, 7-9 Kawran Bazar, Dhaka-1215 (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k).	➤ Created service interruption of e-mail receiving from public/citizen/Profess or Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain without notice.	➤ Investigation and counselling or training of public administration ➤ Administrative follow up of the top management	5000 USD	2025
	Total		55,000 USD	

3.1 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is asking administrative income/penalty income to the department of Bangladesh public service

Table 1, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is approaching a research fund through the public service to Bangladesh government; and/or he is asking to be a chairman of public service commission of Bangladesh government for one term duration. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is proposing the penalty of government officials for their habitual and intentional practice or habitual attitude of official crime under the umbrella of local government under the power of Bangladesh public service commission (M. A. Hossain, 2023c). The penalty may be gradually deducted from the salary. The penalty may be collected one time to continue the job to continue the salary in office. Moreover, it is suspected that the crimes are not casual, the crimes are habitual and regular. Moreover, it is suspected that there is support from the top administration of the relevant government officers. Hence, it is suspected that the crimes are administrative and professional. The departmental assessment and decision should also get priority to establish ethical and democratic principles of a country. Every penalty is also a government earnings or revenue if a government is investing for the magistracy costs and administrative costs if a government is investing to eliminate crimes and criminals. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a paid professor or paid consultant of the relevant ministry or department. So, may Professor Dr. Engr.

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Md. Anowar Hossain ask 50% of this government earnings if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also convincing against the long-term practice of crime by government officers/offices which may eliminate the long-term hassle for the Bangladeshi citizen, if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is applying his professional expertise, which may eliminate the hassle for the Bangladeshi citizen, if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has no registrar to write this report which may eliminate the hassle for the Bangladeshi citizen, if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has no personal assistant to write this report which may eliminate the hassle for the Bangladeshi citizen, if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has no assistant officer or sub - assistant officer to write this report which may eliminate the hassle for the Bangladeshi citizen, if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not using any paid office space of the government to write this report which may eliminate the hassle for the Bangladeshi citizen, if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not using the support of paid top management or paid chain management of a government to write this report which may eliminate the hassle for the Bangladeshi citizen. Hence, every government may encourage to eliminate the crime of local government to increase the revenue in government office to minimize currency inflation or currency printing of a government.

Figure 1. Schematic picture of four copy fifty-taka notes, newly printed money of Bangladesh government (left) and a successor certificate of Mirzapur union parishad (right). In a public service centre, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) paid (four copy fifty-taka notes) to Bangladesh government for a successor certificate without a money receipt copy under the real situation of official dealing, official action and support in the government desk or president representative desk of Bangladesh.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistent. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

3.2 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the crime of additional money of 200 BDT at the office of union parishad, office of Mirzapur Union Parishad, Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh

Table 1 and figure 1; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) invested three official days to collect a warisan (a Bengali word) or inheritance certificate from union parishad or union council. On the first day, administrative officer took an interview and asked about family details as prerequisite of inheritance certificate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Administrative officer also asked the profession of mother as a prerequisite of successor certificate. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain briefly and obediently introduced and answered himself as per the asking of administrative officer. First day, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also showed one ready witness of a local person who signed the application form in front of administrative officer of Mirzapur union parishad. Second day, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted his details of the application form on 17 December 2024. Second day on 17 December 2024, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was obediently and silently waiting around sixty to ninety minutes (total time) for the certificate. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted his details of application form on 17 December 2024. Administrative officer forwarded the application to his subordinate office assistant, who told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “wait in the office room of administrative officer, I am preparing your certificate, you may send a village police to receive the certificate”. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was obediently and silently waiting in the office of administrative officer. In the meantime, administrative officer told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “I can not give you certificate today, there is no electricity today, we need to take the signature of assistant land commissioner. You may come on next Saturday (29 December 2024)”. In the meantime, administrative officer asked 200BDT for his administrative costs and/or personal service in the government office. Immediately and obediently, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain paid 200BDT (four copies fifty-taka notes, figure 1) for the certificate in front of a union parishad member, but the officer didn’t issue any money receipt copy or revenue receipt copy, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain couldn’t understand the issue. If a government officer asks for money, everyone will pay because of their administrative power and/or executive office desk of president. Administrative officer showed the attitude that Dr. Anowar needs to pay for the personal or official costs when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is doing a job in Australia. Therefore, Dr. Anowar left the office of union parishad. Later, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain received the certificate on 24 December 2024 through office assistant of the union parishad. Therefore, may Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also offer a penalty unit from the administrative officer to write this convincing report to the local

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

government. Additionally, administrative officer should pay 5000 USD penalty for writing charge of this report if he is doing service crimes in a government office if he is taking money without the evidence of revenue if the penalty is being supported by the Bangladesh government service act (attached). If the government officer has no minimum shame or hesitation or afraid to do to ask for additional money in front of the public, it seems that the top management is being supported to the designated officers in the local area.

3.3 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the crime of duplicate document preparation of bill/invoice at the office of union parishad, office of Mirzapur Union Parishad, Gopalpur, Tangail, Bangladesh

Figure 2. Three breakages (a, b, c) of newly constructed road from Mohonpur to Mirzapur at Gopalpur, Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistent. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Table 1 and figure 2; on 17 December 2024, in front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; administrative officer was making a duplicate document of a union parishad bill or union parishad invoice of a few workers or payment of casual workers for a road construction or road repairing. A village police was making a duplicate ‘fingerprint’ on behalf of different people on behalf of different local workers. Administrative officer was making duplicate evidence to receive a construction bill on 17 December 2024. Possibly, the bill was around five digits. In the meantime, a bearded man came in the office room who was the democratic member of a union parishad who was unknown to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. The dress code of democratic member in union parishad was Panjabi and Payjama. The administrative officer asked signature to the member of union council on the duplicate document. Union parishad member said, “I do not know anything about this construction; so, I can not sign this document or bill”. Still the member was signing under the request or convince of the administrative officer. These are the symptoms of a cheating practice in a local government office funded by Bangladesh government under the ethical support of public administration. Therefore, the administrative officer should not continue his government duty at Mirzapur, Police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Bangladesh if he is doing any cheating practice subversive of professional ethics, government ethics, and government service. The administrative officer should be terminated from his job immediately if he is confusing the customer service in the local area at Mirzapur union parishad, Mirzapur, Police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Bangladesh. The administrative officer may also pay 5000 USD penalty to Bangladesh government if he is confusing the customer service in the local area at Mirzapur union parishad, Mirzapur, Police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Bangladesh. For a relevant example, a road from Mirzapur to Mohonpur located at Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia was not monitored by the local government and union council. Figure 2, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was looking the road breakage or plaster breakage since 2022. It is a newly constructed road. Practically and physically; I, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.) also saw a few accidents due to road breakage, figure 2c. There were also few accidents due to road breakage, figure 2c. It was also blood-flowing accident due to road breakage, figure 2c. Local people are the sufferer and sufferer. Accordingly, few publics should agree to approve the invoice or bill for specific road construction or breakage construction of the local road. Every local government should have routine monitoring of the road to minimize the repeated construction of the road to minimize the printed money of Bangladesh government. There are approximately 300-400 autorickshaws, 100-200 motorcycles, 50-100 private cars, 50-100 trucks, 1-5 buses are transporting daily for the communication support of the local government. So far, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can remember that he also saw animal transport by animal energy in

1991-2002. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also saw the pulling of transport by cow or horse or man. A road contractor should ensure a longevity guarantee of the local road or the highway road. Maximum roads are curving and curving. They may take specialized consultancy support from the relevant highway engineers or specialized consultants or relevant highway researchers/professors at engineering universities. They may also apply/trial geotextile for the right longevity or long-term longevity of the local roads. We can not waste the printed money of the Bangladesh government. These are the successor wealth of the public of the Bangladesh government. This wealth should be spent by the ethical representative and/or authority of public administration and/or political leaders. Moreover, it seems that the Bangladesh government has also contributed to the construction and improvement of the village roads. When Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was walking in the morning, the road in the village look like Australian park. But the local government has no action and plan for the tree plantation project beside the roads. A tree may also be a financial support of the repairing costs of a local road. A tree may minimize the breakage of the roadside. But these roads are gradually becoming crowded and crowded of transports. These are the regular impact of an uncontrolled population and thenon-planned design of road construction. Every road should be built under the consideration of the long-term planning and crowd impact of transport.

3.4 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the crime at sub-assistant land office of Bangladesh government

Table 1 & figure 5; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain went to local land office of sub-assistant land officer, Mohonpur, Mirzapur union parishad, police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Bangladesh in 2024. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited the office two times. In 2022-2023, sub-assistant land officer asked for the warisan certificate of another people (attached written evidence of sub-assistant land officer, figure 3) against a piece of registered land of Bangladesh government, but he didn't ask the warisan certificate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. What was the official duty of a sub-assistant land officer if he was a representative of Bangladesh president/Bangladesh land ministry? Therefore, sub-assistant land officer misguided to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Officially, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not ask and apply for warisan certificate of other people in Bangladesh. Who should be responsible to improve the administration of land division? Officially, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can only apply for his warisan certificate as a valid citizen. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also asked to sub-assistant land officer, "I am not getting full document of my father's land property, I only got a few documents." Sub-assistant land officer told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, "you need to pay the official cost." But the officer couldn't tell the exact amount of money or the official charge or document searching charge or list of charges for the government service on behalf of Bangladesh government. All official rules and

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

payments should be written, and fixed in front of the government offices. It seems that the amount is negotiable in a government office; the official charge is negotiable under the central revenue support of Bangladesh government. Where is the transparency in revenue in public service in land division? The situation is not public-friendly, government-friendly, and revenue-friendly. Every government charge should be fixed price to ensure the exact revenue of a government to minimize the currency inflation to minimize the currency printing of a government.

Figure 3. Written evidence (Bengali language) of a sub-assistant land officer at Mohonpur, Mirzapur union parishad, Police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Bangladesh whatever misguided to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2023-2024.

On 13 November 2024, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain gave tax on land through the designated local land officer. Sub-assistant land officer also had subordinate office assistant. In front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he was also taking donation money or additional money (around 100 BDT) from the local brother or local public or local customer or Bangladeshi citizen. Similarly, he/his office assistant showed the attitude that he was not getting salary from Bangladesh government. Sub-assistant land officer also asked Australian dollar from Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain for his government service in a Bangladeshi land office. He had also supported voice on behalf of elder brother, Mr. Md. Sanowar Hossain (M. A. Hossain, 2023ba) of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in a government office. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to present and convince his voice in the government office. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain suspected that there was involvement of local criminal. How can a government officer ask 'Australian dollar' in the office of Bangladesh under the attitude of laughing? Accordingly, sub-assistant land officer was showing the attitude of additional money at front desk representative of president. These are the annoying attitude for a Bangladeshi citizen holder in any government office when people are visiting a government office for a specific service or ethical support as a valid citizen holder. The offence should be punishable of 5000 USD penalty. Professor

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get 50% of this penalty of Bangladesh government for his report of convincing about crimes in government office.

3.5 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the crime at office of assistant commissioner (land) and compared the public service with passport office and hospital of Bangladesh government in terms of office time and financial transaction

Page | 20

On 13 January 2025, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited the assistant commissioner (land) office at Gopalpur, Tangail. The distance between sub-registry office, Gopalpur, Tangail and office of assistant commissioner (land), Gopalpur, Tangail is around half to one kilometer. Both land offices should be in one building to ensure public-friendly support at Gopalpur, Tangail. This is the first time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain who visited an office of assistant commissioner (land) in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain went there on first morning at 10-10:30 am. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was waiting in the waiting room under the direction of a help-desk. Land commissioner came around 11:30 am. Accordingly, there was no official announcement or notice in the waiting room. Assistant commissioner had an official dress code of black color coat and tie. It was an official and professional dress code. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain submitted his document to the help-desk for the hearing of mutation of a piece of land at 10-10:30 am. The office of assistant commissioner didn't provide any received copy of the printed copy submission. It seems that the attendance of citizen or customer has no value at government office. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also applied online against printed copy submission. Personally, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was unable to submit an online application form from his personal computer. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain went to a commercial computer shop in Tangail which was commercially serving to fill application form at district commissioner's office area, Tangail. A commercial computer operator was able to submit online application under the telephonic connection with someone with unknown person. Commercial computer operator just telephoned and told someone in front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, "one namzari (mutation) file." Later, computer operator was successfully able to submit the online application form. What is the online situation of land department at Tangail, Bangladesh? Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got an invitation message for a hearing of mutation to come at the office of assistant commissioner on 13 January 2025. Similarly, there were five to eight publics who were waiting in the room of help-desk for the service of land commissioner and/or the office of land commissioner. Possibly, there were office assistants in the office of the land commissioner who were gossiping with the clients. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain couldn't understand their designation by looking at their dress code. Every official and professional person should have a dress code and designation with a nameplate. The nameplate of a government employee may be attached to the shoulder of dress. There was also office stuff in the office of the land commissioner. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain was hearing the azan of Zohr prayer of Muslim community. Muslim people pray at midday at one to two pm under the Muslim invitation and Muslim alarming. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was waiting silently and obediently in the waiting room. The mutation files or submitted files were still waiting in front of the front-desk or help desk person. But the service of land commissioner and/or office staffs were not started at 1:00 pm. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also saw on 10 February 2025 at Gopalpur sub-registrar office when the registrar came around 12pm when there was no alternate official to continue the relevant service. Oppositely, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited the passport office in 2024 at Tangail, they almost finished their public service of front desk by 1 pm. One day, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain went to Tangail passport office after 1: 00 pm, around 1:20-1:40 pm, he couldn't submit his application file. It was the end of the front-desk service of Tangail passport office in Bangladesh. Under the permission, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried to convince a sub-assistant director to allow late submission of a file if there is any provision to allow the late submission at passport office. But the request or approach was not granted or permitted by the sub-assistant director who told me, "come on the next day". This is the symptom of sincerity, officiality and professionalism of a passport office in Tangail, Bangladesh. Again, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain went next day on first morning around 8:00 am-9:00 am. They were servicing around one hundred to two hundred people or more people. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw one office assistant in passport office who was directing the order or sequence of people by 9:00 am. In 2013 and 2019; there were brokers in passport office at Agargaon, Dhaka. Both land office and passport office are government paid offices. In order, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was the second person for the hearing of mutation of a piece of land at land office on 13 January 2024. But later, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was the last person for the hearing of mutation of a piece of land. Hence, there was a lack of administrative management in the land office funded by a democratic government, funded by public administration, funded by the government of Bangladesh, funded by public, supervised by assistant commissioner (land). Around 2 pm, a fatty office assistant (wearing khaki color or brown color coat) asked for 200BDT to a lady public. The words of fatty and dress code are used to identify the person when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain does not know the name and designation. Office assistant told to lady public, "I am not asking 500BDT, I am asking 200BDT only." Office assistant was not afraid to ask for money in the front desk. He was asking for money very simply and simply in a professional attitude of earning money. The lady said to office assistant, "take fifty taka, you are doing a government job." Office assistant was not happy to receive fifty taka note and office assistant denied receiving fifty taka note who didn't take fifty taka note who left the room. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was confused the whole situation in the waiting room of

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

the land office. Every government service should have a fixed price rather than a negotiated price. Every price of land service should be briefly listed and fixed under the government revenue for the cost reimbursement of land commissioner's office for the salary reimbursement of land commissioner's office. It seems that the government salary is not salary, government salary is the fixed deposit in bank, additional earning in government office is the exact salary, additional earning in government office is the target salary is the target income in the land office. Government is not paying salary through the direct hand of the public or citizen, government is paying by bank transfer; this is also a limitation of government administration or public administration to satisfy a government category employee. Later lady public shared and told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in the waiting room, "there was land related meeting in the office of upazila nirbahi officer (UNO). Still, I was facing problems under the involvement of local political leaders. UNO forwarded me to the meeting of local people to solve the land issue." The lady had a dress code of black borka. Possibly, the lady public was approaching and facing the situation of helpless. One local person of Mirzapur union parishad also shared and told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in the waiting room, "I got a piece of warisan land after twelve years court processing, I invested a lot." Possibly Bangladesh court didn't pay or arrange any service charge of the public or victim for his twelve years duration court processing when the victim spent a lot of official hours to get his warisan land property. For example: so far, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain heard from the casual discussion, late father of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also got harassment to get his warisan land property. Later, Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid got land property. Possibly he didn't get victim-friendly compensation for his long-term investment of official hours in Bangladeshi court. He and his family faced financial harassment of Bangladesh government due to a lack of government law and relevant administrative imperfection. (M. A. Hossain, 2023ba). One public was discussing in front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in front-desk in the waiting room on 13 January 2025, "I submitted my land document/file, but the file is missing from the office of land commissioner." These are the symptom of cheating, trapping, and official harassment in a government office. One public was discussing in front of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in front-desk in the waiting room on 13 January 2025, "I am trying for my land mutation, I spent few months to get mutation of my land property." Office assistant was also asking and discussing about the costs and costs of public service with the publics. Office assistant was discussing, gossiping, and telling with public in the waiting room, "if you pay, we will serve you for your land issue, we will serve better for your land." One public told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, "public/private landowner need to pay 20,000BDT to 30,000BDT to the land office for a mutation file without money receipt and revenue evidence of Bangladesh government". Every income should be the government income to develop a country to minimize currency printing and currency inflation. Possibly, these are the symptoms of official offence, habitual offence or regular offence in the office of an assistant commissioner (land) who has a

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

power of magistracy for public who can not apply magistracy to the office of assistant commissioner (land). Assistant commissioner has also magistracy power as mentioned in the nameplate in front of his office room. It was around 2:00 pm. Waiting room was almost empty and empty. In the meantime, one office staff told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “you will get the message, your work is finished now.” Sometimes, a chief executive officer should spend time in the front-desk. These are not a crime. What is the requirement of the front-desk or help-desk in the office of public service in the office of a president representative? What is happening at the front-desk? The number of government employee should be proportionally correct and accurate in the government offices to eliminate the financial crisis and financial cost of a government to minimize currency printing and currency inflation. Sometimes, an unknown managing director also meets with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at the front-desk. But it was the private limited company who was directly responsible for the profit-loss policy of the office of the company who was directly responsible for the self-salary. But government officers are not directly responsible for the profit-loss of self-office or self-country or self-salary or self-administration. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw the managing director, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw the chairman, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw the chief executive officer, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw the general manager, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw the executive director who directly visited their departments and sub-departments. What is the wrong with government offices? What is the uncommon issue with government offices? One laboratory demonstrator of Gopalpur college, Tangail discussed with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in a tea stall in front of office of assistant commissioner (land) and said, “the office of assistant commissioner is making additional money for their public service, possibly they are dividing and share their money of additional income with themselves.” It is also a matter of research and development to improve the government service, if government officer is directly responsible for their salary and monthly income in government office for their daily service if they can earn from their customers, if the policy can be trailed and scrutinized. There is a huge scope of research and development in public service offices and officers when everyone is public, everyone wants peace, every government officer wants peace, every public wants peace, everyone wants to survive in a criminal-free environment in a hassle-free public service. Maximum private companies are comparatively more profitable than the government companies. Maximum government offices are paid by printed money. Practically, government companies should be more profitable than private offices or private companies. Every government office implements and shows more power than private companies. Every ministry is a separate company of a government. Every ministry should be individually liable to ensure the profit to lead the local government office. We need to take care

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

the government offices if we want to survive. Government earnings and functions of a land department should be properly monitored by the central government of Bangladesh. Land department should be a profitable business of a central government. Possibly, Bangladesh government may manage the whole administrative costs through the land business and land office. Government is the owner of the whole land property of a country. Government is protecting the land property and huge investing for defence management of the country. How many people purchased land property from the government? What is/was the standard price of land. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain don't know the exact history. Where is the exact record of the government? Every property may be audited and audited. Somehow, people got the power, ownership and occupancy of the land property. What was the real history? Although, the land property is being sold or transferred in Bangladesh from five-digit to eight-digit BDT per decimal unit of land. There is an enormous lack of land record policy and administration. Publics are the sufferer and sufferer. Land officers are the achiever, earner, and winner. Central administration of the government is blind and blind. What is the real function of the ministry of land and/or ministry of law if there is an existing of paid administration if there is ready administration in Bangladesh? Possibly, there are government limitations and implementations to manage land department and transparency in land documentation in Bangladesh. Bangladesh has a ministry of land which manages and controls the whole department. Bangladesh has minister of land who manages and controls the whole land department. Land offices artificially create the problem. They create the situation of asking money to the clients/public. Possibly, they have good expertise of talking about earning money. If they have expertise to earn additional money, they should survive without government salary. They are getting official and social value for their job and administrative earnings, but they are doing crime in the government office in the name of public service. Who should solve the situation? Which office of Bangladesh should responsible to eliminate official crimes? Land office tries to establish nine equal to six formulas to ask for money from the public. There are so many problems in the land office related to public support. There are so many problems with land documentation related to public support. But, if someone pays money, the designated officer tries to solve the problem. It seems that additional money = solution of problem in the land office. Although they can not solve the problem permanently, they can not think to solve/recommend permanently to the top management to the ministry of land. These are the symptoms of high-risk criminal offence in the land office in the government office. Ministry of land should urgently extend their action and support to take care/ensure the public-friendly support without which ministry of land should not take their salary from the government from the public/citizen to minimize currency inflation of the government.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Table 1 & figure 4, 5; similarly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also confused with the administration of Bangladesh land division. They are still maintaining handwritten documents in their sub-registrar office. Possibly, they are still getting an updated salary structure of government in their sub-registrar office. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited the sub-registrar office in 2023-2024. Landowner or land registry searchers should pay 1000 BDT, 2000 BDT, 3000 BDT, 5000 BDT, etc. to the registry office, Gopalpur, Tangail. These are the searching fees on yearly searching basis. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also asked support from the registrar who was wearing a white colored shirt who was telling to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we will only take government charge of our office”. Accordingly, the registrar forwarded to the office of the concerned assistant officer or staff (male) through a lady office assistant. Assistant officer (male) asked for fifteen hundred BDT for the government charge or fees but Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain paid 1000 BDT (two copies five hundred-taka notes, figure 4) for a document searching of two years for a discount search of two years duration registry record. Sub-registrar office, Gopalpur, Tangail didn't issue any money receipt copy or revenue copy from a government office in Bangladesh but assistant officer was smiling when receiving money when receiving 1000BDT. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also asked for a revenue copy. Office of registrar, Gopalpur, Tangail supposed to reimburse money to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Name of father: Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Bangladesh if the office assistant is getting a salary from Bangladesh government. The offence of office assistant should be punishable of 5000 USD penalty. Similarly, the offence of the registrar should be punishable by 5000 USD. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get 50% of this penalty of Bangladesh government. It is a matter of shame for Bangladeshi citizens when there are no rules about who is taking the government money in the name of searching the land register from a government record book. A national ID (identity/identification) number and a minimum land detail should be enough to search the last landowner or a record of a piece of the local land. Last owner of a piece of land should find out by one click by one minute in a computer. Possibly, it is possible to make the whole document by six to twelve months duration project of land registry of Bangladesh government. Population is increasing and increasing. Land dividing is also proportionally increasing and increasing in Bangladesh. The application and planning of long-term housing rules are very minimal. The application and planning of long-term agricultural lands are also very negligible. There is nobody to monitor. Every government should try to minimize land dividing or land ownership on behalf of the land ministry which may minimize the future hassle or difficulties of the land ministry. Five to ten decimal units should be the minimum land size for private ownership. Ownership

transfer/sell between private and government, ownership transfer/sell between private and private, ownership transfer/sell between the land ministry and government organizations should be more transparent and income-friendly which may increase the income of the land ministry which may minimize the currency inflation in Bangladesh. It seems that government land is not a land. It seems government office is the personal office of a land officer who can charge and earn additional money from the office. But Bangladesh government is liable to pay the monthly salary of land ministry. Accordingly, a specialized team should serve for the future planning of land department. For example, Dhaka city was an unplanned city and a naturally built city without future planning for a quality survival. Now we can not control the planning of Dhaka city but we are making a high-rise bridge or overbridge or flyover bridge to eliminate the present crisis of Dhaka city. Every flyover bridge is very expensive and expensive. We should also invest for a long-term plan and quality research for quality planning of a city and village. Definitely, and possibly, we are investing the printed money of Bangladesh government and/or the revenue of Bangladesh government. Still, we can not solve the issue for quality surviving in Dhaka city. Possibly, we should make a plan to make a second Dhaka city in a separate location. Possibly, we should propose a new capital city in a separate location to minimize natural disasters and/or accidents in future. Different important offices and universities may be immediately shifted to the new Dhaka city to the new places for a quality survival. Every fifteen to twenty years, the capital city may be replaced to minimize the density of people, house, and offices in Dhaka city to minimize the price of land in Dhaka city.

Figure 4. Schematic picture of two copy five hundred-taka notes of Bangladesh government. In a public service centre, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) paid to Bangladesh government without a money receipt copy and revenue evidence under the real situation of official dealing and official support under the official discussion with the registrar of sub-registry office at Gopalpur, Tangail. But the official charge was not a fixed price. But the official charge was the charge of Bangladesh government.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Figure 5. Assistant commissioner (land) should be responsible to follow-up the sub-assistant officers, local sub-registrar office; and union parishad council instead of elected chairman of union council in 2024-2025. Every public care centre of assistant commissioner (land) asked additional money for their government service. This is the symptom of public harassment in a public nursing centre.

Figure 5, 6; normally Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain goes to a private doctor or clinic for their private and specialized service. By chance, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain visited Tangail Medical College Hospital for his dental treatment. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain paid a five taka note for the revenue or income support of the Bangladesh government or hospital. Similarly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain saw that the different people were also paid. Immediately, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got a money receipt of five taka. He didn't ask for a money receipt copy. Firstly, he paid a five-taka note. Secondly, the concerned person gave him a ticket or money receipt against a five-taka note. Comparatively, the cost in a private clinic or private doctor in Bangladesh is 100-200 times more expensive for one-time consultation fees. Although, lower-income people can not afford accordingly. Every private clinic may also have an option for the support of the lower-income people. Dr. Nadia Sharmin was serving in the dental care or patient consultation unit of Tangail Medical College Hospital who

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

recommended the private clinic who commented and told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we have no facilities for filling of teeth, you may go to private clinic.” Later Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain asked to Dr. Nadia Sharmin, “which private clinic do you prefer for the treatment?” Possibly, Dr. Nadia Sharmin was not interested to tell. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain repeated asked to Dr. Nadia Sharmin. Then she told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “you may go to Sonia Clinic.” Dental treatment is comparatively expensive. Later, Dr. Anowar got the paid service of a private clinic. So, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to recommend to improve the dental facilities in Tangail Medical College Hospital of Bangladesh government. If a hospital has no dental treatment facilities in a medical college hospital, the central administration should not say it medical college hospital. At least, if the service can be cheaper for the lower-income people of the Bangladesh government. Therefore, every surgical facility may be improved in the government medical centre for the cost minimization support of lower-income people. Every surgery should be the final treatment of a medical practitioner. Surgery should not be the way of tendency of additional earnings of a medical practitioner. Every alternative should recommend to the patient if the guidance is better for the patient. It is also being noted that Bangladesh needs to continue research and development for lower-income people. Why are they poor? Bangladesh can not just continue the free-of-cost support of lower-income people in a government hospital. But a government can not support to a non-planned family unit or non-planned lower-income people in general. Bangladesh needs to continue; Bangladesh needs to contribute the research and development to eliminate lower-income people. Indirectly, every public/citizen is also bearing and caring the costs of the lower-income people in the name of government hospital and/or public hospital and/or public care and/or social support. Indirectly, every professional person is also bearing and caring the costs of the lower-income people in the name of government hospital and/or public hospital and/or public care and/or social support.

Figure 6. A prescription of a five taka note in a hospital of Bangladesh government. In the corner of the prescription, there is also a seal of five taka for a transparency record. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain acknowledge to Bangladesh government to

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

manage a minimum health treatment and service by five-taka note. This is a symptom of contribution and social support to the lower-income people.

Table 1 & figure 5, 6; if a hospital or passport office can issue a money receipt copy or a revenue copy on behalf of the Bangladesh government or hospital or passport & immigration office. What is the restriction or exemption with the land office or union council office that can not issue a money receipt if they have taken any special permission from the concerned ministries of the country? But the office orders and practices should be transparent and public-friendly. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain does not know accordingly. These are the direct responsibilities of the district commissioner (DC) and UNO. Upazila nirbahi is a Bengali term for the chief executive officer of an upazila, the designation of upazila nirbahi officer in Bangladesh may be edited as sub-district commissioner. Bangladesh government officially and gradually increases the salary of the government employees. Bangladesh government increases salary in the name of promotion. Bangladesh government is ensuring multidimensional facilities in different ways. Bangladesh government is ensuring and paying multidimensional allowances in different ways. Bangladesh government takes care of the retirement facilities of government service holders. Bangladesh government is taking lifetime responsibilities of government service holders. However, Bangladesh government is trying to pay under the capability and survivability of Bangladesh government and citizens. Bangladesh government is still paying to government officers when Bangladesh has a financial hardship. Still, Bangladesh government should not take the responsibility to pay additional salary or payment or ready cash in the public offices or front desk or the representative desk of president of Bangladesh government on behalf of the public. But the local publics are not getting salary for the administrative follow-up of the government officers. But the top administration or chain administration or district commissioner or relevant ministry is getting a salary for administrative follow-up of the government officers and administration. Non-paid public should not take official responsibilities for the administrative follow-up of the government officers. Bangladesh government should regularly and sincerely calculate and monitor the percentage of inflation to satisfy the increment of the government salary. Every employee should get a standard marriage/sex/accompany allowance. One husband or one wife should get a standard marriage/sex/accompany allowance in a couple family. Maximum offices are ready to make sex harassment, but the offices have no marriage/sex allowance. Under the present situation of democracy in Bangladesh, every elected and selected category political leader should get a lifetime safety allowance. It is also necessary to have a proper financial audit of the salary, earnings, allowance, and cost to make a force to eliminate crime in public service from the office assistant to chief executive officer of Bangladesh government (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024i, 2024s, 2024x). Therefore, government officers should not take single dollar/single

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

taka from the public without money receipt evidence or revenue evidence of Bangladesh government. Government officers should not take single dollar/single taka in the name of job, special service, junior service, senior service, political service, public service, and promotion in office. The offence should be highly punishable like the termination of the job, imposing penalty unit, ceasing the money of retirement, ceasing the house and land property, ceasing the money of bank account, physical punishment, and lifetime imprisonment. In special cases, a government criminal may have a special penalty, such as the death penalty (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). If the recommendation prefers the terminating the job, the chain administration may take money from the crime offender, the chain administration/top administration may transfer the designated officer instead of termination of job. So, what will be the benefit of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) who is reporting and investing his official time to eliminate the crimes of public nursing centre in Bangladesh? Somehow, we are all serving together for the peace for a quality survival in the society in the country in the planet. Every public and government officer may contact with Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, Barrister (Dr.) if they are facing harassment in government offices.

3.6 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the crime at First Security Islami Bank (FSIB) of Bangladesh

Figure 7, FSIB cheated with Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in 2024. The bank was unable to pay money for the fund crisis. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has been maintaining the account since 2017, he had a five-digit amount of money in the bank account. Therefore, he managed his money from another source. His total financial compensation was around 500 USD in Bangladesh when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain managed his money from another source when he had no way to manage money from another source. Due to bank interruption in 2024, bank administration of FSIB or governor of Bangladesh Bank had no general notice or message for the client support or bank account holder of FSIB. It was supposed to make a scope to make a plan by the account holders. But the situation continued and continued for the long-term duration. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was begging and begging for the money at FSIB. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was moving and moving to different branch of FSIB. But the different branch manager or account branch was unable to pay money. The branch managers were repeatedly blaming to the government conditions and the central order of the bank management of FSIB. Manager, Vuapur Branch, FSIB, Vuapur, Tangail told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we have no money, do not eat my job, we have nothing to do”. Manager was sitting in the dining corner instead of his room of manager to hide himself to protect himself from the violence of customers. Manager, Ghatail Branch, FSIB, Ghatail, Tangail told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we have no money, FSIB is trying to manage government or governor.” Manager, Hamidpur Branch, FSIB, Hamidpur, Tangail told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we have no money”. Manager, Tangail Branch, FSIB, Tangail

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we have no money”. Manager, Ashulia Branch, FSIB, Savar, Dhaka told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we have no money”. Manager, Motijheel Branch, FSIB, Savar, Dhaka told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “we have no money”. Sometimes, they also paid 2000 BDT/5000 BDT under the force request again and again to the branch manager. Sometimes, manager/officer also forwarded or recommended to the different large commercial branches or the main account branch of FSIB. The manager or officer made a false recommendation about the large commercial branches or the main account branch. Still, there was a fund crisis in large commercial branches or the main account branch. Governor of Bangladesh bank; chairman and managing director of FSIB should not deny their responsibilities of public service and bank administration of FSIB. These were also symptoms of cheating and harassment to the bank customers in Bangladesh. The penalty for the bank harassment should be 5000 USD. The FSIB should pay 5000 USD to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. If Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had ethical earnings, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should get the proposed penalty amount of 5000 USD through the appropriate authority if the authority can believe the bank situation and harassment to customer. This penalty should impose to the FSIB bank. Accordingly, every account holder may get a minimum amount or lump sum amount of a penalty unit to satisfy the ethical service of FSIB if FSIB is getting support of newly printed money of Bangladesh Bank if FSIB is getting support of Bangladesh government to continue their repeated business if the account holder faced harassment if the account holders were sufferer and sufferer. Every government is richer than a local businessman. Every government has a right to print money, but a local businessman can not print money. Therefore, every office should be transparently liable for the public service to the Bangladesh government. Figure 8: every government should run their business or service to minimize the currency inflation to maximize the national and international transparency.

Sl #	Bank Name	C. A/C #	Chq. Account#	Instrument	Amount	Currency	Business Date	Reason
1	ISLAM BANK LTD	600613610110	0012200002933	2150497	48,000.00	BDT	13/09/2024	Item required revalidation
Total					48,000.00			

Figure 7. Evidence of legal crime of FSIB and evidence of online bank rejection of bank transfer to Sonali Bank Limited at court building branch, Tangail.

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Figure 8, how does the public pay to the government through the gradual scenery of currency inflation when every public or citizen is the successor of the government's wealth in a democratic country? If the political violence and unethical practices are the root of currency inflation, the government needs to solve the issues ethically and urgently. Inflation is also a major issue for the performance of a political leader, public administration, and government running policy. Nobody likes to hear the word of 'bankruptcy' from the governor of the Bangladesh bank. This is so much annoyance word for national and international community. These should not be the dream of the Bangladeshi people or the political leaders or public administration or bank administration. Anyhow or anyway, Bangladesh government needs to find out the root of 'bankruptcy' to eliminate the currency inflation. Bangladesh government needs to continue the research and development for the right survival. Nobody should cease the money of Bangladesh government. Nobody should have a way to cease the money of Bangladesh government. When Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain goes to bank, the bank is not paying his deposited money. It is a matter of shame and shame of every democratic government. Bangladesh Bank should be liable to reimburse the wealth of the public. How a private bank can get more money than their deposited amount or their existing wealth? Who is take caring the bank? Who is controlling the Bangladesh Bank? Who is controlling the FSIB? It is also necessity to improve the banking policy and transparency. Related bank specialist should also make more research about national and global money printing policy. They should make a local campaign/public campaign. Practically, if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has one billion USD, he can not take a bank loan more than 1 billion USD, he may take a specific percentage of his total money or wealth. In general, when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has no wealth to show, he personally can not take a bank loan, he can not take single dollar/single taka from the locker of the local bank or Bangladesh Bank. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain tried and tried in Bangladesh for his textile business in 2016. Presently, he invested the whole of his money for education in Australia. Practically, he has no visible money now. But he can not take bank loan by showing his wealth of education and professional achievement. Every bank prioritizes visible money rather than the wealth of education and professional achievement. So, legally there is no chance of 'bankruptcy' of Bangladesh government. The word 'bankruptcy' should be banned from the Bangladesh government. If it is continued and continued, local people may be interested in investing or depositing to foreign countries. A bank manager, Vuapur Branch, Sonali Bank Limited, Tangail told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain regarding the crisis of FSIB, Bangladesh (2024), "we should not keep the chance of the corruption to eliminate bank crisis and/or any corruption in Bangladesh". Accordingly, and possibly, Bangladesh needs to calculate the wealth before the joining date and the retirement of every person in the public service. In general, every bank provides a money receipt copy for their acceptance of money. In 2022, Sonali bank, Ashulia Branch, Dhaka didn't provide any money receipt (around 100 BDT) for their online service when Professor Dr. Engr.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vivellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Md. Anowar Hossain deposited money to his bank account from another branch. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was confused for their service but he just paid to proceed the action and support of the bank.

Figure 8. Dr. Anowar’s theory of currency inflation of a country.

3.7 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the crime at post office of Bangladesh government

In 2016-2017, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was forwarding letters through the government post office at Ghatail, Tangail, Bangladesh. Receptionist or document receiver asked for additional money for their public service. The document receiver told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “pay for the refreshment of my sir, we will proceed your document.” These are the words of habitual practice in government nursing/service centres. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain didn’t pay accordingly. In 2022-2023, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain paid additional money to the general post office, Gulistan, Dhaka for their public service. In 2013-

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

2015, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain sent a parcel from Kolkata, India to Niagara Textiles Limited, Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain properly packed the parcel. He self-hand packed and wrapped the parcel. But the parcel goods were missing from the parcel under the government postal service of India and Bangladesh. So, there are enormous limitations and corruption in the government offices.

3.8 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the symptom of crime of the top administration at government offices of Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got the electronic mail (e-mail) back of the sent e-mail of different government offices in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also got automatic failure notices of twenty-one e-mail addresses of office of president (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k), office of chief advisor (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k), office of university grant commission (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025b), office of human rights commission of Bangladesh government and different important offices in Bangladesh. The e-mail addresses were collected from the active website of the mentioned officers/offices. Every e-mail address and website should be monitored and modified regularly. The government offices had no reply message of the acknowledgement of the letters in 2024-2025. Every government e-mail address should be active to ensure the public service of the government without which the concerned offices/officers should approve and pay a penalty to the client. This should be a penalty of 5000 USD for service interruption in government offices without any notice. Every government office is expensing the government money, expensing the money of the public. Every government office should have a necessary action to ensure the public service. All government officers are busy serving the country. Similarly, all publics are also busy and busy to serve the country. Parallely, all publics are also serving for the government in different offices. So, the government is standing and running. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to attach an example of a list of failure e-mails through failure notices of an active government in Bangladesh. These are the symptom of failing a government policy of failing a democratic policy of failing a job responsibility and public caring. Possibly, nobody can complain to the government for their power of the permanent job, power of their regular salary and allowance, power of the government support, power of the autocracy in the name of democracy, power of their office desk, power of their chair and table, power of the office of president representative, power of their chain community, power of their political involvement and other relevant issues.

3.8.1 Failure Notice-01

Yahoo/Inbox

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.2 Failure Notice-02

Yahoo/Inbox

www.yahoo.com

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (ps_president@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.3 Failure Notice-03

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<director_research@ugc.gov.bd>:

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (director_research@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.4 Failure Notice-04

Yahoo/Inbox

Page | 36

www.yahoo.com

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (secretary@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.5 Failure Notice-05

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<chairman@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (chairman@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.6 Failure Notice-06

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (secretary@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

Page | 37

3.8.7 Failure Notice-07

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<pschairman@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (pschairman@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.8 Failure Notice-08

Yahoo/Inbox

www.yahoo.com

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (press.secy@bangabhaban.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

3.8.9 Failure Notice-09

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.10 Failure Notice-10

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:39 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<nazmul@ugc.gov.bd>:

550: permanent failure for one or more recipients (nazmul@ugc.gov.bd:554 rejecting banned content)

3.8.11 Failure Notice-11

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.12 Failure Notice-12

Yahoo/Inbox

From: mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To: engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<jamery.hasan@cao.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.13 Failure Notice-13

Yahoo/Inbox

From: mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To: engr.anwar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ddresearch@cao.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.14 Failure Notice-14

Yahoo/Inbox

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<lutfey.siddiqi@cao.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.15 Failure Notice-15

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<psecy@cao.gov.bd>:

3.8.16 Failure Notice-16

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<secretary@cao.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.17 Failure Notice-17

Yahoo/Inbox

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<seafath.mahmud@cao.gov.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.18 Failure Notice-18

Yahoo/Inbox

From: mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<chairman@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.19 Failure Notice-19

Yahoo/Inbox

From: mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<ftm@nhrc.org.bd>:

554: rejecting banned content

3.8.20 Failure Notice-20

Yahoo/Inbox

www.yahoo.com

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<musfiquldu33@gmail.com>:

550: 5.1.1 The email account that you tried to reach does not exist. Please try

5.1.1 double-checking the recipient's email address for typos or

5.1.1 unnecessary spaces. For more information, go to

5.1.1 <https://support.google.com/mail/?p=NoSuchUser> af79cd13be357-7be6146cc77si721835785a.122 - gsmtip

3.8.21 Failure Notice-21

Yahoo/Inbox

www.yahoo.com

From:mailer-daemon@yahoo.com

To:engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Sun, Jan 19 at 3:38 PM

Sorry, we were unable to deliver your message to the following address.

<syrawarn@gmail.com>:

550: 5.1.1 The email account that you tried to reach does not exist. Please try

5.1.1 double-checking the recipient's email address for typos or

5.1.1 unnecessary spaces. For more information, go to

5.1.1 <https://support.google.com/mail/?p=NoSuchUser> 6a1803df08f44-6e1afbafac5si68904606d6.88 - gsmtip

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

3.9 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) remarked the crime at foreign ministry of Bangladesh government

At the front desk of the foreign ministry, Bangladesh; Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was hearing the noise of 200BDT payment or negotiation. Possibly it was a negotiation in terms of file submission support of the front desk. It was a discussion between a receptionist and a client or public when Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was waiting around 1 minute at the front desk of a government service centre of a representative of president. On 4 February 2025, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also asked the front desk of the foreign ministry to meet with foreign secretary. The receptionist told to Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, “Mr. Md. Jashim Uddin, secretary is not present in office, he is in a foreign tour.” Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain requested an appointment as a public or as a citizen. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain got a receiving seal and signature of the requisition of the appointment letter on behalf of the front desk.

3.10 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is remarking official representation, quality control, and liabilities in public service

May Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain recommend to notifying this report to all Bangladeshi government employees who are serving the public who are dedicated for their public service who feel prestigious for their public service who get social honor in the society for their public service who get salary for their public service who tell to people, “I am an officer, I am an engineer, I am a commissioner”. Land-related official writing, medical prescriptions, post office writing, and money receipt copies should be clear, visible, computerized, and public-friendly. A primary school student should be able to read or spell. Sometimes, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain can not understand or spell the English letters in a medical prescription of a qualified medical practitioner in Bangladesh. It seems that a patient/pharmacist should get proper training to read a medical prescription, a land owner should get proper training to read the registry documents of land in government offices. These are annoying. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain observed in 2022-2024 in Bangladesh. A bank transfer or bank deposit form may be initiated for land business and land-selling process in Bangladesh. Somehow, every citizen of any government is sincerely monitoring the dedicated service of the government officers and government offices. In some places, we are public in a country. In some places, we are officers in a country. In some places, we are political leaders in a country. In general, we are in the same pipeline to survive as a unit of human being as a unit of a country. If there is any hole in the pipeline, everyone will be impacted, everyone will suffer. People should not forget accordingly. If we are the unit of public, if we are the unit of the public service commission; if we are destroying

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

government wealth of any country, we are increasing the government cost, we are also responsible for increasing the currency inflation of the country.

3.11 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is remarking about administrative chain and executive post versus crimes of local government in Bangladesh

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain suspects that the government crimes are being practiced and continued under the illegal support. There are two chains of a democratic government. Parallely, one chain is administered by the political leader, and another chain is run by permanent government officers or public administration. Possibly, the whole chain is affected by coronavirus disease 2019. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is afraid and afraid about the right implementation and scenery of public service. Officially, we can change or replace political leaders by election council by selection council by democratic principle, but we can not replace the permanent government officer. These are the permanent limitations of the democratic government of a democratic country. Possibly, the right principle of a democratic government is being hampered. Therefore, the report may be circulated to the chairman, secretary, government officer, political leader of every union council, city council, and relevant top administration and chain authorities of Bangladesh government. Hence, may Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain seek support or recommend to ensure ethical service and ethical practice of Bangladesh government. Possibly, everyone like additional money. Every baby also like money. Every mad people also like money. But the way should be formal, official and ethical. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is not a paid professor or consultant of a local government of Bangladesh. But he is facing harassment in government offices; he should get a compensation award from Bangladesh government. This is a matter of right official counseling or right official training, or right official practice for the government officer for the peace of Bangladeshi citizens. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to propose the ethical flavor to develop the attitude of the government officers. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain highly believes that the office of the local government is serving accordingly. As a valid national ID holder, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain should have a legal right to ask for ethical platform in government offices.

3.12 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist, (Dr.) Barrister (Dr.) is commenting about salutation in public offices and right practice of democracy rather than mobocracy and autocracy

Every public service officer gets a value in the society for their designation for their service to the public. In general, public service officers believe that the people at the top or chain administration are respected, and public service officers call them 'sir/madam'. But the people of 'public/citizen' are not 'sir/madam'. But the public has no value to the government officers. But the top management has a high value to the government officers. But the top management can cease the

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

job. But the public can not cease the job. But we should not forget that we are the officers of public or citizens. We are the officers of public if we are the unit of public service commission. The post of public officer is created for the public service; the post is not created for the top administration or chain administration. We may also call or salute the public by 'sir/madam'. This should not be a crime. This is democracy rather than mobocracy and autocracy. At different times, public visits government offices; public usually salutes government officers for their ethical standards and honour in their high job responsibilities in a government platform. Under the social situation of the communication, public also says or calls or salutes them with 'sir/madam' or 'Mr. X' or 'Ms. Y' or 'title + name' or 'assalamualaikum' or 'good morning' or 'good afternoon' or 'thank you' or 'hello' or 'hi'. Although, assalamualaikum is also a Muslim salutation preferred by the Muslim community. Mr./Ms. is also a very common salutation. In a government or social culture in Bangladesh, public can not/do not directly call by name of an executive officer. People also maintain designation in family office or social life journey for social survival. In family office, people call by name to junior, title + name, mother, father, brother, sister, uncle, aunt, grandfather, grandmother, etc. Possibly, public officers can similarly apply in the government office if they are the member of human being. But there is also limitation of exact age or unknown age. In general, people respect people by two-dimensional belief by age and profession. Profession is the self-achievement of a person. Age is the natural achievement of a person. Age is the automatic achievement by birth. So, high-professional-category people get more value than a high-aged person. If the person is senior by post in an office but junior by age, what should be the salutation to the subordinate people who are senior by age? Everyone should also implement exactly and officially to satisfy the subordinate people in an official platform. For the example of greeting in office, one of friend or classmate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in BSc engineering class said to a lady assistant professor, "you are like mother". Possibly, the lady teacher was not happy who immediately replied, "do not say like mother, say like madam". Maximum case in whole life journey of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, he didn't see any government officer in Bangladesh is saying 'sir/madam/Mr./Ms' to their customer or client or public or Bangladeshi citizen holder. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain does not know the exact legal acts in Bangladesh. What should be the exact rules? Possibly, there is no legal acts. Every citizen should be highly respected by the government officers. There is necessary to establish the exact salutation of both party under the government act under the ministry of public administration. Every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre or public nursing centre. A government office should not be a gathering centre or cheating centre or trapping centre or additional earning centre. Every government officer sit in a chair and table to ensure a quality service on behalf of a government on behalf of public or citizen. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar

Hossain also saw sofa in the office room of a sub assistant director in a government office. Who should seat in the sofa? Possibly public or customer should seat in the sofa for their comfort feeling or cushion feeling or respect in front of a public officer. Possibly, keeping a sofa in front of a public officer is the symptom of social respect to the public or citizen, this is not a respect to the government officer to keep few chairs in front of a government officer. People should not forget this if we are government officer if we are paid employee of any government or organization. Such way every party should be highly respected or supported for local surviving for local government as part of human being. These should not be a matter of known person or unknown person or very important person or educated person or business class person of any party. Both parties may salute as sir/madam if these are the popular terms or common terms in the official platform if we don't know the exact age of the person. Historically, sir was also used as title. Possibly, 'sir' was the representative persons of king/queen in autocracy. So, the salutation should be replaced for democracy. Historically, king/queen got high quality government facilities. Still, their housing are the historical visiting places in Bangladesh, India/British India. Their design of housing is the representative of a museum. It seems that the king/queen highly dominated the people/public/citizen for their quality lifestyle. Still now, this is not replaced by democracy. Under the democracy, 'sir' is the representative of public. In a public office, a government officer may also salute and tell to the public, "sir/madam, how can I help you?" This is the practice of democracy to ensure the service to the general people to respect the democracy. If government officer can say and serve accordingly, these are not a symptom of crime in an official environment if government employees are showing or respecting the government service if government employees are respecting their daily income source if government officers are respecting their profession if government officer is respecting his/her promotion if government employees are prioritizing the public or customer if government employees are official and professional if government officers are sincere and dedicated for the peace of public or citizen if government officers are respecting the principle of democracy. Democracy means the quality support to public and quality surviving theory. Democratic government practices and ensures the equal opportunity to the public. If we go to a vegetable shop or a fruit shop or garment shop, they are so much alert, they are so much sincere, they are so much obedient to sell their product. Shopkeepers try to ask or call willingly, eagerly, and sincerely, such as: hi/hello. They are not higher educated person. But they try to show a sincere attitude to run their self-business to respect their income source. Bangladesh government didn't invest to make educated them. But some government service holders are not serving accordingly when they are selling their ethical service on behalf of a democratic country. Under the democratic philosophy, every government service is paid by public. Every public is the legal beneficiary of the government. So, we are saying public service. So, we are saying public administration. So, we are saying public service commission. So, we are saying democratic government. So, we are arranging election and selection process under the philosophy

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

of a democratic government. Practically, it seems that every political government is taking lease a country for a specific time duration to govern a democratic country to implement a democratic theory under the election and selection policy (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024w). The democratic principle is not only a matter of election, selection, and campaign when every election, selection, and campaign are expensive and expensive. All over the world, the actual democratic process of election, selection, and campaign have huge limitation. Research and developments are very minimum and minimum. We are still neglecting the democratic principle but we are saying the democracy but we are doing advocacy but we are practicing autocracy in the name of democracy. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is the inventor of a new democratic theory (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024w). Every democracy should be public-friendly. Every qualified public is a quality source of quality income and quality development of a democratic country. Every public is earning. So, every government is earning. Every public is developing. So, every government is developing. Every year, a percentage of a government earning may be proportionally distributed to the bank account of public in different way in terms of the quality service of the citizen in terms of quality grading of the citizen. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain also proposed the categories of democratic leaders. Internationally, every democratic election commissioner or director or executive may assess the theory of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) for the right edition and implementation for the right dream of a democratic government under the democratic election and selection process of any country (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024w).

If Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) print all of his sole authored publication, he can not self-carry his self-publication by himself; if Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain get all of his archived money/earned money in his profession in Australia and Bangladesh in the currency note of 100USD, he can not self-carry his self-money by himself (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024x). So, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should get honour by the principle of democracy, he should get honour as public, he should have legal right to ask honour as Bangladeshi citizen, he should have right to ask honour in government offices. He should not face any illegal harassment in any office in Bangladesh. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) should not face any situation to pay additional money in Bangladesh. Every crime and every criminal should be banned should be banned in Bangladesh. Let's establish zero crime in public administration to lead a democratic government.

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

3.13 Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is shouting and shouting to make a practice of criminal free world for surviving in the planet for the extension of human lifetime

It seems that the crimes and criminals are everywhere. It seems that the crimes and criminals are full and full in the government office. Every government should eliminate professional crimes, seniority crimes, performance crimes, sex crimes, promotion crimes, appointment crimes, nomination crimes, political crimes, force crimes, verbal crimes, parenthood crimes, professorship crimes, designation crimes, health crimes, officer crimes, and other relevant crimes in government offices. Let's shout and shout for a criminal-free world. Every family member should disrespect criminal and crimes. Every person should disrespect the criminal and crimes. Every organization should disrespect the criminal and crimes. Every country should disrespect the criminal and crimes. Every political leader should disrespect the criminal and crimes. Every government office should disrespect the criminal and crimes. Every secretary should disrespect the criminal and crimes. A mother is a prestigious post in a family office, so we can not protest the crime against mother, so we can not say anything. A father is a prestigious post in a family office, so we can not protest the crime against father, so we can not say anything. A president is a prestigious post in an office, so we can not protest the crime against president, so we can not say anything. A chief executive officer is a prestigious post in an office, so we can not protest the crime against officer, so we can not say anything. So, I am writing and writing, I am campaigning and campaigning to establish zero crime theory and zero corruption theory all over the world. The practice of zero crime may bring the exact peace and heaven to the society for a quality survival on the planet. Peace and heaven bring the extension of the lifetime of the people.

3.13.1 Cited Australian federal register of legislation, Australian public service (APS) act 1999 and Bangladesh public service (BPS) act 1860 for approaching penalty to government officers in Bangladesh for self-earning of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain, 2023c)

Section 15: breaches of the code of conduct

Sanctions that may be imposed

(1) An agency head may impose the following sanctions on an APS employee in the agency who is found (under procedures established under subsection (3) of this section or subsection 41B (3) or 50A (2)) to have breached the code of conduct:

- (a) termination of employment;
- (b) reduction in classification;

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

- (c) re assignment of duties;
- (d) reduction in salary;
- (e) deductions from salary, by way of fine;
- (f) a reprimand.

Note: See sections 29 and 38 in relation to terminating an APS employee's employment.

(2) The regulations may prescribe limitations on the power of an agency head to impose sanctions under subsection (1).

Providing false or misleading information etc. in connection with engagement as an APS employee

(2A) A person who is, or was, an APS employee is taken to have breached the code of conduct if the person is found (under procedures established under subsection (3) of this section or subsection 41B (3) or 50A (2)) to have, before being engaged as an APS employee:

- (a) knowingly provided false or misleading information to another APS employee, or to a person acting on behalf of the Commonwealth; or
- (b) willfully failed to disclose to another APS employee, or to a person acting on behalf of the Commonwealth, information that the person knew, or ought reasonably to have known, was relevant; or
- (c) otherwise failed to behave honestly and with integrity;

in connection with the person's engagement as an APS employee.

Note: If the person is an APS employee at the time a finding referred to in paragraph (2A) (a), (b) or (c) is made in relation to the person, the agency head of the employee's agency may impose sanctions on the person as permitted by subsection (1).

Procedures for determining whether APS employee, or former APS employee, has breached the Code of Conduct etc.

(3) An agency head must establish written procedures in accordance with this section for determining:

- (a) whether an APS employee, or a former APS employee, in the agency has breached the code of conduct (including by engaging in conduct referred to in subsection (2A)); and

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

(b) the sanction (if any) that is to be imposed under subsection (1) on an APS employee in the agency who is found to have breached the code of conduct (including by engaging in conduct referred to in subsection (2A)).

(4) The procedures:

- (a) must comply with basic procedural requirements set out in commissioner's directions; and
- (b) must have due regard to procedural fairness.

(5) In addition, and without affecting subsection (4), the procedures may be different for:

- (a) different categories of APS employees or former APS employees; or
- (b) APS employees, or former APS employees, who:

(i) have been convicted of an offence against a Commonwealth, state or territory law in respect of conduct that is alleged to constitute a breach of the code of conduct; or

(ii) have been found to have committed such an offence but no conviction is recorded.

(6) The commissioner must issue directions in writing for the purposes of paragraph (4)(a).

Note: See section 42 for general provisions relating to commissioner's directions.

(7) An agency head must ensure that the procedures established under subsection (3) are made publicly available.

(8) Procedures established under subsection (3) are not legislative instruments.

The penal code of BPS, 1860 (ACT NO. IX OF 1860, 161, 162 of Bangladesh, chapter IX of offences by or relating to public servants

161. Public servant taking gratification other than legal remuneration in respect of an official act: Whoever, being or expecting to be a public servant, accepts or obtains, or agrees to accept, or attempts to obtain from any person, for himself or for any other person any gratification whatever, other than legal remuneration, as a motive or reward for doing or forbearing to do any official act or for showing or for bearing to show, in the exercise of his official functions, favour or disfavour to any person, or for rendering or attempting to render any service or disservice to any person, with the government or legislature, or with any public servant, as such, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Lecturer & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

162. Taking gratification, in order, by corrupt or illegal means, to influence public servant: Whoever accepts or obtains, or agrees to accept, or attempts to obtain, from any person, for himself or for any other person, any gratification whatever as a motive or reward for inducing, by corrupt or illegal means, any public servant to do or to forbear to do any official act, or in the exercise of the official functions of such public servant to show favour or disfavour to any person, or to render or attempt to render any service or disservice to any person with the government or legislature, or with any public servant, as such, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

The penal code, 1860 (act no. XLV of 1860, 120B, 415) of Bangladesh

120B. Punishment of criminal conspiracy: (1) Whoever is a party to a criminal conspiracy to commit an offence punishable with death, [imprisonment for life] or rigorous imprisonment for a term of two years or upwards, shall, where no express provision is made in this Code for the punishment of such a conspiracy, be punished in the same manner as if he had abetted such offence. (2) Whoever is a party to a criminal conspiracy other than a criminal conspiracy to commit an offence punishable as aforesaid shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term not exceeding six months, or with fine or with both.

415. Whoever, by deceiving any person, fraudulently or dishonestly induces the person so deceived to deliver any property to any person, or to consent that any person shall retain any property, or intentionally induces the person so deceived to do or omit to do anything which he would not do or omit if he were not so deceived, and which act or omission causes or is likely to cause damage or harm to that person in body, mind, reputation or property, is said to "cheat".

Australian trade practices act 1974 (Cth)

75AZI Certain misleading conduct in relation to services

(1) A corporation must not, in trade or commerce, engage in conduct that is liable to mislead the public about the nature, the characteristics, the suitability for their purpose, or the quantity, of any services.

Penalty: 10,000 penalty units.

**Your Honour, Please Pardon me
 Best Regards for your excellency for the peace of mankind**

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Anowar

7 July 2025

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.),
Barrister (Dr.)

Office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.),
Barrister (Dr.)

PhD student ID: 3820066, 512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, RMIT University,
Melbourne, Vic-3056, The Commonwealth of Australia.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Permanent residence by birth

Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (postal code: 1990), police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia; nationality, national ID (membership ID of prime minister selection committee and president selection committee of Bangladesh government), passport and birth registration number: Bangladeshi (by birth), 19862692620993890, A15988852 (present)/ EE0444946/AF3831770 (previous), 003236.

4 Author contribution and authorship status of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.)

The author is self-declaring the profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.); PhD & Postdoc in terms of conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, experimentation, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

5 Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

6 Funding

The author received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

7 Data availability

All data generated during this research are included.

8 Notes of exemption in the research of applied law and criminology for zero crime approach for the peace of mankind

The criminal/criminals/crime/crimes/people/peoples is/are international. The crime history is original and practical in PhD and Postdoc journey of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at RMIT University, Australia. In the research of applied law and criminology, the relevant human assessment, names, case studies, and organizations have been cited and implemented

- ✓ to protect the data information of crimes and criminals for the international category judicial assessment
- ✓ to show the practical evidence of crime and criminals
- ✓ to protect the people to ensure human defence and human peace in international platform
- ✓ to ensure the safety of relevant people and/or organizations and/or professor community and/or researcher community and/or RMIT University, Australia
- ✓ to notify crime courts, judges, review boards, judicial board, human rights, united nations, and relevant international communities
- ✓ to continue research and development
- ✓ to circulate the outcomes of academic research
- ✓ to approach zero crime for the peace of mankind

9 Acknowledgement

Sole author, chief director (PhD research), chief director (defence project) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc;

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023ao; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (M. A. Hossain, 2023ah, 2023al, 2023bi, 2023cg, 2023ch) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2023; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023g, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm; M. A. Hossain, 2023a; M. A. Hossain, 2023bn, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs; M. A. Hossain, 2023b; M. A. Hossain, 2023bt, 2023bu, 2023bv; M. A. Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; M. A. Hossain, 2023bw, 2023bx, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025); name of father: late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, medical practitioner; permanent residence (PR): village: Purbo Nuthurchar, post office: K. Mohonpur (1990), police station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); nationality, national ID, passport and birth registration number: Bangladeshi, 19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, program name: DR213, PhD (fashion and textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; lecturer on textile engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2025. Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.) (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges ‘Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and ‘Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>) for their PhD supervision works at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Author acknowledges every contribution and support in his life journey,

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

academic organizations and teachers, professional organizations and colleagues, researchers, professors, and people from nursery schooling to PhD and Postdoc schooling to be Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain; Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.).

Profile links of Author

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Abbreviations and glossaries

Additional earning: the informal and illegal earning against the revenue of Bangladesh government

APS: Australian public service

BDT: Bangladeshi taka

BPS: Bangladesh public service

E-mail: electronic mail

FSIB: First Security Islami bank

ID: identity/identification

Public service: public service means the nursing/caring to public or citizen for the genuine peace of public. Public service does not mean the forcing to public and earning money from the public in different techniques of crime and trapping.

UNO: Upazila nirbahi officer or sub-district commissioner

USD: United states dollar

Warisan certificate: Warisan is a Bengali word, successor certificate, a government beneficiary of birth rights/family rights. If a person has a family rights/birth rights beneficiary of less than the amount of minimum surviving, he/she should get a government subsidiary of job support, food support, and living cost support of a government.

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

For showing honour, for the excellency of PhD schooling; a copy of this report is also being forwarded (randomly sequenced) to

Professor Dr. Lijing Wang, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

Page | 56

PhD student ID: 3820066, 512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, RMIT University, Melbourne, Vic-3056, The Commonwealth of Australia.

lijing.wang@rmit.edu.au

Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks, RMIT University; PhD supervisor of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

PhD student ID: 3820066, 512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, RMIT University, Melbourne, Vic-3056, The Commonwealth of Australia.

robert.shanks@rmit.edu.au

robert.shanks.scientific@gmail.com

Mr. Md Shihab Rayhan, Deputy Director, Local Government, District: Tangail, Bangladesh
ddlgtangail01@gmail.com

Advocate Md. Asaduzzaman, Chairman, Bangladesh bar council

info@barcouncil.gov.bd

Central library of Bangladesh

cdlbd21@gmail.com

British library, United Kingdom

customer@bl.uk

Library, RMIT University, Australia

repository@rmit.edu.au

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCRC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Office of the Registry, High Court of Australia

Registry@hcourt.gov.au

Professor Dr. SMA Faiz, Chairman, University Grant Commission, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh Page | 57

fakhrul@ugc.gov.bd

secretary@ugc.gov.bd

syrawarn@gmail.com

nazmul@ugc.gov.bd

director_research@ugc.gov.bd

ferdousugc@gmail.com

chairman@ugc.gov.bd

mustafiz@ugc.gov.bd, mustafizugc@gmail.com, pschairman@ugc.gov.bd

Brig Gen Prof. Dr. Engr. Md Lutfor Rahman (Retd), Vice Chancellor, City University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

vc@cityuniversity.ac.bd

registrar@cityuniversity.ac.bd

Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, The Commonwealth of Australia

vc@rmit.edu.au

brooke.griffin@rmit.edu.au

ea.vc@rmit.edu.au

jason.ngam@rmit.edu.au

nicole.hendrie@rmit.edu.au

alec.cameron@rmit.edu.au

alec.cameron@aarnet.edu.au

Dr. AKM Saiful Islam, City University, Dhaka, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh

s.islam05@gmail.com

saiful.bste@cityuniversity.ac.bd

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Professor Dr. AK Samanta, University of Calcutta, Kolkata, West Bengal, The Republic of India
ijtaksamanta@gmail.com
ijtaksamanta@hotmail.com

Professor Dr. Swapon Kumar Gosh, University of Calcutta, The Republic of India
ijtskg40@gmail.com

Page | 58

Professor Dr. Sadhan Chandra Roy, University of Calcutta, The Republic of India
sadhan53@yahoo.co.in

Ms. Nardia Simpson, Acting High Commissioner of Australia, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
ahc.dhaka@dfat.gov.au
consular.dhaka@dfat.gov.au

Foreign Minister and/or Foreign Secretary, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
fs@mofa.gov.bd
dirfso@mofa.gov.bd
ssa@mofa.gov.bd
aswelfare@mofa.gov.bd
dgcnw@mofa.gov.bd
dirwelfare@mofa.gov.bd
asconsular2@mofa.gov.bd

Barrister A.M. Mahbub Uddin Khokon, President, Bangladesh Supreme Court Bar Association, Shahbag, Dhaka-1000.
scba.bd@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Forhad Hossen, Dean, Dyes and Chemical Engineering Department, Bangladesh University of Textiles, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
head@dce.butex.edu.bd
butexdce@gmail.com

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vivellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Absar, Jahangirnagar University, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
abserju@yahoo.com

Dr. Md. Emran Hossain, Department of Law, City University, Dhaka, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
ehossainsau@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Ayub Nabi, Pro Vice Chancellor, BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
provc@buft.edu.bd

Barrister Sarwar Jahan Shamim, Supreme Court of Bangladesh
bshamimsc@gmail.com

Ms. Tasmima Hossain, Editor, The Daily Ittefaq, The Peoples Republic of Bangladesh
ittefaqdigital@gmail.com
ittefaq.adsection@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Mahbub Ullah
Convener, Interim Committee, Bangladesh Economic Association, 4/C, Eskaton Garden Road, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh
bea.dhaka@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Mihir Kumar Roy, Economist
mihir.city@gmail.com

Ms. Sharifa Haque, Deputy Commissioner & District Magistrate, Tangail, Bangladesh
dctangail@mopa.gov.bd

Registrar office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, enr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (enr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: \$12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Page | 62

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Reference

Anowar Hossain, A. K. S., A. Bagchi, Kashmita Bhattacharya. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications, American Association for Science and Technology (AASCIT), USA*, 2(4), 25-34. <https://documents.pub/document/simultaneous-dyeing-and-fragrance-finishing-of-cotton-simultaneous-dyeing-and.html?page=1>

Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>

Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01. <http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>

Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>

Hossain, A. (2023). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assisist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assisist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assisist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, A., Islam, A. S., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from Swietenia macrophylla and Musa Acuminata as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent. *Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 3(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.03.000558>

Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. (2019). Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers. *Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering*, 4(4). <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Effect-of-Variation-in-Different-Mechanical-Setting-Hossain/9402f52697c08f2b6104abb07e1f4f414aa3f332>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650>

Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online), USA*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>; <https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>

Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., Bhaumik, N. S., Vankar, P. S., & Shukla, D. (2018). Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distilled Organic Extraction of Organic Tectona grandis and Azadirachta indica with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 2018(1), 1-12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21790.51524>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245102>

Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 8(5), 1-5. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Non-toxic-Coloration-of-Cotton-Fabric-using-and-Hossain-Samanta/76a9a8128bc038db760f2b93328e4eefeb2ae4d1>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>

Hossain, A., Sun, D., & Samanta, A. (2019). Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. *JResLit Journal of Science and Technology*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15079.62880>; https://pure.hw.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/92968499/Modern_Technology_versus_Rapid_Economical_Growth....pdf; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245107>

Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709410>

Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology*, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>

Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29667.94247>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241586>

Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer*, ISBN-978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>

Hossain, M. A. (2010c). *Principle of garments production*, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>

Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13304637>

Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments* (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28804.50568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311367>

Hossain, M. A. (2015c). *Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments* [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India.]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854437>

Hossain, M. A. (2018). *Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles* (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17899.31521>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311345>

Hossain, M. A. (2019a). Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 8(89).

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11724.18561>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242756>

<http://www.ijsei.com/archive-88919.htm>

Hossain, M. A. (2019b). Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(4).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00204>

Hossain, M. A. (2019c). Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn. *South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(2).
<https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.36346/sarjet.2019.v01i02.002>;
https://sarpublication.com/media/articles/SARJET_12_43-49_c.pdf

Hossain, M. A. (2019d). Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18112.75524>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850320>

Hossain, M. A. (2020). My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>,
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>.

Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47. <http://pubs.sciepub.com/materials/9/1/3/>

Hossain, M. A. (2021b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination* (Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>

Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.101537>

Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370.
<https://publications.drdo.gov.in/ojs/index.php/dsj/article/view/17731/7785>

Hossain, M. A. (2022b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background* (Presented in humanities and

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

- social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). 50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286740>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023c). Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics. *Scholarly Community Encyclopedia*. <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49095>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29805.15844>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7944616>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223162>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anowar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management.* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25788.21120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240631>

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vivellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anwar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

- Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709555>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12923.49448>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238071>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15879.16801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238806>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19654.04160>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35625.16486>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8232618>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16822.88641>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239492>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240371>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,

- Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240383>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240507>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023r). *Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27465.93280>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240547>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Anowar's Handbook on Industrial Economics*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34176.81925>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240589>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Anowar's Handbook on Machine Technology & Maintenance of Wet Processing Machineries*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22432.76802>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240660>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14883.02082>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240703>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Anowar's Handbook on Microprocessor, Robotics and Control Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26627.07204>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240796>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar,

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: S12.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17714.17602>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240984>

Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19391.89763>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241043>

Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Physics (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17294.74561>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15613666>

Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Project Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35461.32480>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709510>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241631>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ab). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing & Quality Control (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23166.77121>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241394>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241291>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241183>

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233503>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29857.99683>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233914>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). *Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV), publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; supported by the act of University Grants Commission of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286913>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ah). *Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023; Valencia, Spain, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ai). *Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023; Rome, Italy, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aj). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023al). *Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297554>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh: ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, M. A. (2023am). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>

Hossain, M. A. (2023an). *Conference Presentation on “Camouflage Engineering and Camouflage Textiles for Defence Technology”*; 2023 Philippine Textile Congress, Future Thinking for Philippine Textiles, Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI), Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO), General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631, Philippine; *Speaker during the Textile for Human Security and Defense Session (Session 8) of the Congress on 20 November 2023; Accepted.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.22407>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117340>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ao). *Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square 1-18.* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ap). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aq). *Decision of RMIT University against Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye did a conspiracy to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ar). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747451>

Hossain, M. A. (2023as). *First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>

Hossain, M. A. (2023at). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind.* a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,

- engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023au). *Letter of study leave extension for PhD research works from 1st November 2023 to 31 October 2025, designated for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15384.16648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862986>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023av). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Polymer Science & Engineering.* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31974.80969>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240852>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aw). Md. Anowar Hossain, Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ax). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on "camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds"* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ay). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970344>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970310>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970241>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>

Hossain, M. A. (2023be). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bh). Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bi). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bj). *Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). *An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm (Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Issue*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8298582>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bo). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311145>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University;* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bq). *Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286771>

Hossain, M. A. (2023br). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Scholarly Community Encyclopedia.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.* <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), M.Tech (CU, India), B.Sc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCME College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vivilatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

- Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318727>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate*

- dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>*
- Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>*
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068327>*
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>*
- Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cb). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cc). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>*

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc²
 Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia),
 PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color
 engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile
 & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of
 BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence
 research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime,
 crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high
 court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king
 of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament,
 government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education,
 research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal
 consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India, Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<http://www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cd). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ce). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions; Accepted in Advanced Material Research (2019-2020). *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia* (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of*

- PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024a). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024b). Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024c). Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024d). Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024e). A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024f). Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds” School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024g). Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024h). Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024i). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning. R. U. School of

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vivilatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

- Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Tech (India & Bangladesh), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Prof and Engr (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
 PhD & Postdoc in Textile Tech, Technical Textiles & Color Engg
 PhD & Postdoc in Applied Law
 PhD researcher ID: 3820066, RMIT, Melbourne, Australia
 MTech in Textile Tech (Technical Textiles & Color Engg)
 University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International research consultant: R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Lecturer & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vivellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
CV, success in research of Prof. Anowar; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, BSc in Textile Tech
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection* [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>

Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>

Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>

Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

Hossain, M. A. (2024aa). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>

Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government* [Grant]. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>

Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Hossain, M. A. (2025c). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a*

Barrister (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 7 July 2025.

- legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>
- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Absar, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245079>
- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. K. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-cost-minimization-process-of-heat-and-energy-for-Hossain-Samanta/145246a45b40a7ef33c3e37cc99083f91f6555fa>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>
- Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, D. S., Barrister (Dr.). (2025). *Journal of Dr. Anowar*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29003.30243>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550150>

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

By birth, every person is the beneficiary or successor of the government wealth and/or family wealth. By nature, nobody can carry his/her wealth after death. Therefore, by nature; somehow, everyone is enjoying the wealth of death peoples from the source of family and/or country. So, every government office should be a customer care centre or client service centre all over the world. So, every government office should ensure/improve food safety and living cost support for the citizen to run the government system.